

Supplementary files of chapter 2 The Use of Pictograms in the Evaluation of Functional Abdominal Pain Disorders in Children.

Supplementary table 1. Differences in demographics and clinical characteristics between patients originating from the Netherlands and Belgium (as assessed by the clinical expert).

Characteristic	Netherlands (n=108)	Belgium (n=36)	p -value
Age, median (IQR), y	14.0 (12.0 – 16.0)	12.5 (11.0 – 14.0)	.029
Female, frequency (%)	66 (61%)	21 (64%)	.240
Male	42 (39%)	12 (36%)	
Randomization			.567
Questionnaires without pictograms	63 (58%)	19 (53%)	
Questionnaires with pictograms	45 (42%)	17 (47%)	
Diagnosis, frequency (%)			.000
IBS	35 (50%)	2 (6%)	
FAP-NOS	24 (34%)	2 (6%)	
FD	9 (13%)	4 (12%)	
AM	1 (1%)	0	
Other*	1 (1%)	27 (77%)	
Missing	38	2	
Symptoms, frequency (%)			
Epigastric pain	67/108 (62%)	27/36 (75%)	.157
Epigastric burning	27/108 (25%)	20/36 (56%)	.001
Bloating feeling			
Pre-prandial	31/108 (29%)	9/36 (25%)	.692
Post-prandial	35/108 (32%)	22/36 (61%)	.006
Abdominal pain (lower quadrant)	94/108 (87%)	25/36 (69%)	.016
Severe intense abdominal pain	92/108 (85%)	18/36 (50%)	.000
Burping or flatulence	39/107 (36%)	17/34 (50%)	.372
Nausea	52/108 (48%)	23/36 (64%)	.238
Vomiting	16/107 (15%)	12/36 (33%)	.049
Regurgitation	33/108 (31%)	24/36 (67%)	.000
Stool frequency past month, frequency (%)			
≤ 2 times a week	8/103 (8%)	1/36 (3%)	.446
≥ 3 times a week	95/103 (93%)	35/36 (97%)	
Bristol Stool Scale, frequency (%)			
BSS 1 / BSS 2	8/105 (8%)	3/35 (9%)	.088
BSS 3 / BSS 4	56/105 (53%)	24/35 (69%)	
BSS 5 / BSS 6	15/105 (14%)	6/35 (17%)	
BSS 7	1/105 (1%)	1/35 (3%)	
Alternating	25/105 (24%)	1/35 (3%)	

*Other diagnosis included cyclical vomiting syndrome (CVS), eosinophilic oesophagitis, functional constipation, gastritis, gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) and gastroparesis. Abbreviations: IBS: irritable bowel syndrome; FAP-NOS: functional abdominal pain – not otherwise specified; FD: functional dyspepsia; AM: abdominal migraine; BSS: Bristol Stool Scale.

Supplementary table 2. Concordance levels for gastrointestinal symptoms between clinical expert ratings and patient ratings using questionnaires or questionnaires with pictograms

Symptoms	Questionnaire	Questionnaire +
	(n=82) k - value	pictograms (n=62) k - value
Epigastric pain	0.44	0.54
Epigastric burning	0.55	0.40
Bloated feeling		
Pre-prandial	0.47	0.37
Post-prandial	0.47	0.24
Abdominal pain (lower quadrant)	0.54	0.31
Severe intense abdominal pain	0.51	0.50
Burping or flatulence	0.56	0.30
Nausea	0.34	0.58
Vomiting	0.45	0.55
Regurgitation	0.39	0.54

Reproducibility was considered fair, moderate, substantial or almost perfect if the Kappa coefficient was respectively 0.21– 0.40, 0.41–0.60, 0.61–0.80 and > 0.81.